

How to build a low-cost and user-friendly meteorological device for mobile thermal comfort mapping

This “how to” document details how to assemble a low-cost and user-friendly climate monitoring device for handheld mobile measurements with the aim of spatially identifying areas of thermal discomfort.

Device schematic:

How to assemble the device:

Prepare the main parts as listed below and the miscellaneous assembly parts. Prepare tools including: a soldering iron, solder, drill, drill bits and a Dremel type tool with a small cutting disk, as well as basic tools such as a screw driver, an Allen key, and tap set.

Main parts:

Item no.	Description	Manufacturer	Manufacturer p/n	Supplier	Supplier p/n
1	Selfie stick	Insta360		Amazon	B07Y5ZH5SM
2	Cheese plate	SMALLRIG		Amazon	B07Y5ZH5SM
3	Junction box	SAMENGTR		Amazon	
4	Bolt kit	Dana Fred			B09BKTHHKP
5	Adalogger	Adafruit	2796	The Pi Hut	ADA2796
6	SD card	Qumox		Amazon	B07F7VZTMY
7	GNSS Breakout	SparkFun	GPS-15733	Unmanned Tech	14F-35E-1E4
8	RTD Amp	Youmile		Amazon	MAX31865
9	Push button			The Pi hut	102788
10	LiPo	PKCELL	LP503035	Pimoroni	BAT0003
11	Transistor socket	Fischer Elektronik	TF54	CPC	SC10686
12	IR Sensor	Melexis	MLX90614ESF-DCI-000-SP	Digikey	
13	Pressure sensor	DFRobot	SEN0423	The Pi Hut	SEN0423
14	Temp / Hum sensor	Sensirion	SHT85	Mouser	SHT85
15	Sensor Socket	Preci-Dip	851-87-004-10-001101	Digikey	1212-1346-ND
16	Pitch changer	Chip Quik inc	F127T254P04	Digikey	F127T254P04-ND
17	Radiation shield	Davis instruments		Weather spares	7345.228
18	Pyranometer	PM Ecology	PK_SSR2AD Sensor	PM Ecology	PK_SSR2AD Sensor
19	12 v PSU	Pololu	U3V40F12	The Pi hut	POL-4016
20	Globe	LabFacility	XE-6332-001		
21	Antenna Ceramic			Amazon	B07MHGPT8
22	USB-C 2.0 to USB-A Cable			Amazon	B085S9XSRB

The Selfie Stick is screwed into the cheese plate to carry the assembled device.

SMALLRIG Cheese Plate with 1/4" and 3/8" Threads.

The SAMENGTR ABS Junction Box IP65 Waterproof PVC -100 x 68 x 50, will hold the main electronics.

The Bolt Nut Assortment Kit Set M2 M3 M4, will be used to standoff the circuit boards from other boards inside the main housing.

The M0 Adalogger is the microcontroller which runs the control software.

The MicroSDHC Memory Card is inserted into the device to log data and can be removed when necessary to transfer the collected data.

Drill two small holes in both sides of the box's front face, and use a Dremel with a cutting disk to make a small slot. Drill larger holes at the front and rear to allow access to the SD card and the USB connection. Slot height is governed by small stand offs which hold the rear two mounting holes of the logger PCB. Attaching the rear standoffs temporarily to the rear Adalogger mounting holes will give a rough height for the slot. Once the slot has been made, the PCB at the SD card end will fit into the slot. This will help mark the place where the two small standoffs will be attached to the box.

The smaller holes' standoffs can be screwed into small holes drilled in the base. 4 larger standoffs are required to hold the GNSS board. They can be drilled and tapped for better fitment. Two larger holes are drilled along the centre line to allow a bolt to hold the box onto the cheese plate. An additional hole in the upper RHS corner allows for a cable to exit the box to the temperature and pressure sensors.

Solder connections between the Adalogger and the SparkFun GPS Breakout - NEO-M9N, U.FL (Qwiic). Data sheets can be seen for more detail on the connections which are: + 3.3 v, ground, SDA and SCL. Wiring details are commonly available for Arduino type projects. Some glue from a glue gun will help prevent the wires being stretched and becoming detached during assembly.

Configure MAX 31865 for the type of RTD used, in this case a 3 wire PT100. The links need to be soldered: fit the screw terminals supplied for PT100 connections F-/F+, the terminals should face in to the centre of the board as the board will be mounted at the boxes edge.

Then drill holes for the standoffs to hold the Amplifier Module Max 31865, these standoffs are an intermediate height between the smaller ones used for the Adalogger and the larger ones used for the GNSS module.

6 x 1/4" Diameter x 1/2" Long 20 TPI UNC Button Head Bolts

Solder wires between the Adalogger and the MAX 31865 Amplifier, SCK to CLK, MOSI to SDI, MISO to SDO. Solder from the + 3 v and GND from the unused pins on the GNSS module to the MAX31865 to bring 3 v to the Amplifier.

Drill two holes in the lid; one for a push button and one for a cable compression gland

16mm Illuminated Pushbutton - Red Latching On/Off Switch

LiPo Battery Pack - 500mAh

Snip the red power cable and solder each cut wire to the push button contacts and seal with heat shrink tubing. When the Button is depressed power will be enabled to the device, or if powered by the USB to a pc/ charging device, depressing the button will charge the LiPo battery.

Attach a 200 Ohm resistor to the led contact of the illuminated push button and seal with heat shrink tubing. Connect the other end to Digital out D6, this will give an external signal for the device's operation.

Take a long premade cable with Qwiic connections, cut off one allowing a few centimetres of remaining cable.

Solder the short cable with Qwiic connection onto a longer cable about 1 m in length with similar sized wires such as alarm/telephone cable matching colour if possible and seal with heat shrink individually and over all connections. At the other end solder the wires onto the TF54 transistor socket in accordance with the Melexis MLX90614 data sheet.

Seal the soldered joints individually and overall with heat shrink tubing.

Feed the socket through another 16 mm cable gland and attach the Infrared thermometer.

Adjust the gland so that no wires can be seen, a piece of half inch tubing sealed in place with heat shrink will prevent damage to the sensor. The Qwicc end can then be fed through the other cable gland in the box lid and plugged into the vacant Qwicc socket on the GNSS module.

Attach socket 4POS 0.05 GOLD PCB to the SHT85 temperature and Humidity sensor

Solder pitch changer 1.27 MM TO 2.54 MM to the socket

Mount the BMP390L Digital Barometric Pressure Sensor on the Davis Vantage Vue ISS Radiation Shield

Drill holes and fit standoffs to the radiation shield either from brass or plastic. Attach the long side of the previously cut Qwiic cable into the remaining free Qwiic socket in the GNSS module, bring the other end through the hole in the upper RHS of the main electronics box and through a newly drilled hole in the radiation shield RHS.

Use header pins to solder wires onto. Solder the power and ground coming from the Qwiic cable onto the pins labelled VCC and GND. Solder the SDA and SCL cables from the Qwiic connector onto the corresponding header pins which protrude above and below the PCB, SCL and SDA.

The pitch changer PCB is then soldered onto header pins which are protruding from the rear connection to the PCB, labelled 3V3 and GND. Remove the device during soldering. Pin 2 of SHT85 VDD is then connected to 3V3 and Pin 3 VSS is connected to GND. Pin 1 SCL is then soldered from the corresponding header pin beneath the BMP PCB as is pin 4 SDA, to its appropriate SDA pin on the BMP.

A hole drilled in the bottom IR shield plate and a large plastic bolt will connect the IR shield to the cheese plate.

The IR shield does not come with the plastic rods used here to connect all the plates together and must be purchased separately. These are 250 mm NYLON Plastic threaded rod, M3 X 250 mm.

The top plate is used to carry the pyrometer, which is mounted on standoffs. A combination is used to keep the pyrometer flat on the sloping top plate. Screws from underneath the plate hold the standoffs in place.

The supply cable to the pyrometer is fed through the cable gland in the box lid to the appropriate connections. The brown cable is the Analog signal and is soldered to pin A1 through a resistor potential divider network. Formed by a 1K and a 2 K Ohm resistor, this prevents the zero to 5 v dc Analog output of the pyrometer ever reaching above 3.3 v, the maximum input voltage to the Adalogger. The brown cable goes into a 1 K Ohm Resistor the output of which is soldered to A1, also soldered to A1 is a 2 K Ohm resistor which is soldered to the previously unused ground terminal on the Adalogger.

The Yellow cable is the + 12 v dc supply and the white the – or ground. These are fed direct from a 12 v dc power adapter which in turn is supplied with 3.3 v dc from the previously unused terminals on the GNSS board.

12V Step-Up Voltage Regulator U3V40F12

The PT 100 temperature sensor is inserted into the globe thermometer housing and the terminals fed through the cable gland to the MAX 31865 amplifier, crimp connections are cut to facilitate insertion into the screw terminals.

The globe can be attached by a bracket onto a metal extension adapter which screws into the cheese plate.

Tripod 6 “metal extension ¼ “x 20, camera adapter

The DollaTek 28dB High Gain GPS Active Ceramic Antenna is attached with the provided rear sticker onto the main control box side and a small hole drilled in the box to feed the connector into the GNSS module

Great care is required when assembling all the parts into the box as there is little spare room, the Adalogger, GNSS module and Max31865 all screw onto their standoffs. The battery is positioned under the top plate and the 12 v regulator is placed in the only other free space.

Programming and operating the device:

Pictured below is the final assembled device. The device is programmed with the Arduino IDE software, using the code from the following repository: Arduino IDE code for a low-cost and user-friendly meteorological device for mobile thermal comfort mapping. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11242382>

To operate the device, insert the SD card into the slot, and press the red button. The button will flash three times upon starting and then every 10 seconds to indicate that data is being collected. Once data collection has been completed, depress the red button and remove the SD card which can be inserted into a computer to retrieve the data.

The data is then available in csv. format with information on: Time, date, latitude, longitude, air temperature, relative humidity, air pressure, global irradiation, surface temperature, and globe temperature.

Data sheets to aid fabrication

SHT 85 Sensirion

https://www.sensirion.com/media/documents/4B40CEF3/61642381/Sensirion_Humidity_Sensors_SHT85_Datasheet.pdf

SSR2AD PM Ecology

https://www.measurementsystems.co.uk/docs/SSR2AD_Specification%20EN.pdf

BMP390 Bosch

<https://www.bosch-sensortec.com/media/boschsensortec/downloads/datasheets/bst-bmp390-ds002.pdf>

MLX90614 DCI

<https://www.melexis.com/en/documents/documentation/datasheets/datasheet-mlx90614>

Max31865 Analog Devices

<https://www.analog.com/media/en/technical-documentation/data-sheets/MAX31865.pdf>

NEO-M9N Ublox

https://content.u-blox.com/sites/default/files/NEO-M9N-00B_DataSheet_UBX-19014285.pdf

Adafruit M0 Adalogger

<https://www.adafruit.com/product/2796>

12 V PSU

<https://www.pololu.com/product-info-merged/4016>